

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Norqulova Risolat

NOGIRON FARZANDI BOR OILALARDA OTA ONALAR O'RTASIDAGI MUNOSABATLARNING YECHIMI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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